

PHYSICAL TRAINING OF YOUNG ATHLETES

Bavatov Fayzulla Shamuratovich

Teacher at the Department of Mass Education in Social and Humanities
of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7898155>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th April 2023

Accepted: 04th May 2023

Online: 05th May 2023

KEY WORDS

*Society. physical _ abilities.
physical _ qualities.
physiological. morphological.
sports, acrobatics. athletics.*

ABSTRACT

This article contains discussions on the development of healthy, physical ability, and physical culture of the promising young people of the society, that is, our future.

Society development present stage young athletes preparation issues separately importance occupation reached is going Our country and chetel of specialists series studies physical preparation problems dedicated. _ Theirs most of them basically big old in porters physical qualities (strength. speed. endurance and others) education laws surface to issue will be directed. Young athletes physical preparation of sports training the most important structural from the parts considering the body in every way development. health strengthening. physical abilities improvement and of preparation all another types for strong functional base to create directed process as is understood. Of the person physical culture formation in the process practitioners _ actions and they are with depends knowledge only by mastering it not staying. own physical they also develop their abilities. Current at the time the possibilities of human action description for., physical abilities" and., physical adjectives from the terms" is used. These are concepts known in a sense similar _ if there are. but one different they are not Unfortunately. in the literature this of concepts definition and mutually _ connection about somewhat opposite thoughts meeting can _ For example. one in case physical abilities in the movement activity of the organism participation doing and his effect defines functional systems of ability manifestation to be forms as understood (GGNatalov. 1977), in another in life. especially in movement activities done to be increased and basis physical adjectives organize which to a person special opportunities mean is caught (APMatveev. 1991), in the third abilities means the organism psycho-physiological and morphological characteristics based on developed born ability badges understood (EPil'in. BVEvstrafev. 1987). Physical abilities- that of a person this muscle activities requirements answer giving and his efficient fulfillment which provides mental and physiological and morphological characteristics is complex. Human movement capabilities separately aspects to express for long time. physical (moving) qualities _ _ term used. Now some the authors him.,

physical Soda formalastic of the concept of "adjectives". content because of scientific from handling out to send and their instead of only., physical the term `abilities" to apply offer are doing Nevertheless. the diary in speech and scientific and methodical in the literature this term much wide spread _ That's why for maybe this _ _ two concept between similar _ and different sides identify. of them use situations set get is appropriate. Modern sports athletes physical preparation high requirements he ate. This at home factors with explain can :

- 1) In sports of achievements grow up always going _ from the athlete abilities development new requires a degree ;
- 2) Physical of preparation high level training _ and competition downloads increase necessary condition. Applied _ of means effect show feature and direction according to physical preparation common physical preparation (UJT), assistant and special physical to training (MJT) types being is studied.

Young of athletes common physical readiness (UJT) is high to the results reach for foundation is necessary basis is considered It is below tasks solution to do aimed at :

- 1) Age athletes in the body functional opportunities increase _
- 2) Physical qualities - strength. speed. endurance. dexterity development ;

Young athletes in the body physical in development defects no _ to do

to the composition of UJT extremely various districts tools enters ; they are in turn

shells with performed in partnership special on devices done to be increased exercises. various sports - acrobatics. light athletics. sports games. swimming and to others special perfume developer there are exercises. Young of athletes helper physical preparation special physical abilities to develop directed efficient activity for necessary has been functional the basis surface to bring is intended. He is special direction _ have being the following solution to do aimed at :

- 1) of an athlete to the chosen sport in specific movement activities manifestation will be functional opportunities development ;
- 2) of the organism high level special to downloads endurance ability improvement ;
- 3) recovery of processes passing away intensity gain _

Young of athletes special physical training (MJT) chosen sport according to competition of activity characteristics to put requirements strictly compliance did without physical abilities to develop directed. Young athletes special physical preparation the following tasks solution will :

- 1) chosen sport is suitable for _ physical abilities improvement;
- 2) on the chosen sport successful technical-tactical improvement for necessary movement skills _ by deepening development;
- 3) specialized exercises in execution more _ participating separately muscle groups choose development. Young MJT movement skills of athletes in the system the most important movement qualities to develop will be directed. That's why for special physical of preparation main tools in case competition exercises their sportsman to the organism effect Different amplifiers _ complicating elements with together is used.

References:

1. O. V. Goncharova. Young of athletes physical abilities Development : Education _ manual. Tashkent, 2005-176b.
2. L. A. Djalilova. Physical education and sports history : Study _ manual. Tashkent. 2015-173b.